

POLICY BRIEF - VERSION 1

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Author(s)	Markus Schmidt, Sandra Youssef, Marjan de May
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AI: Artificial Intelligence

ANVISA: Brazil's National Health Surveillance Agency

DNA: Deoxyribonucleic acid

EFSA: European Food Safety Authority

FDA: US Food and Drug Administration

GMO: Genetically modified organism

ML: Machine learning

REACH: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

1 PREFACE

First version of a policy brief comprising what the project is hoping to do in the regulation plane aiding non-specialised audience (e.g. policy makers) to make informed decisions.

1.1 Background

Artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) and synthetic biology are among the most transformative fields of the 21st century, each reshaping industries from healthcare to agriculture to environmental sustainability. The convergence of these fields is expected to allow for groundbreaking innovations. Synthetic biology, which involves redesigning organisms for specific purposes, can benefit immensely from the predictive and optimization capabilities of AI. In turn, AI systems can be enhanced by insights derived from biological processes, leading to more robust and adaptable computational models.

deCYPher explores the synergy between AI and synthetic biology, investigating how AI can accelerate the design and engineering of biological systems, while also examining how biological systems can improve AI/ML systems architectures. As synthetic biology continues to advance, AI's role in automation and optimizing the design of synthetic organisms, systems, and processes will be critical. The goal of deCYPher is to design novel metabolic pathways in microorganisms to produce highly valuable biomolecules such as terpenoids and flavonoids that have a wide range of applications ranging from medicine to pharmaceuticals, food additives to flavours, fragrances to biostimulants.

1.2 Aim

The integration of AI with synthetic biology holds the promise to contribute to solving some of the world's most pressing challenges in sustainability, energy, and healthcare.

The relevance of this research is underscored by its potential to revolutionise key sectors in Europe, aligning with the EU's vision for sustainable development, technological leadership, and global competitiveness. As Europe seeks to strengthen its position as a leader in the digital and green economy, harnessing the combined power of AI and synthetic biology could provide solutions to long-standing challenges such as resource scarcity, climate change, and public health challenges. This policy brief aims to highlight the strategic importance of investing in AI and synthetic biology research, exploring the opportunities and challenges at the nexus of these fields, and providing actionable recommendations for European policymakers to foster innovation, secure investments, and ensure the safe and ethical development of these cutting-edge technologies while reducing existing barriers to bringing these products to market.

1.3 Process

The development of this policy brief will follow an inclusive and iterative process, beginning with the creation of a first draft (see chapter 2) that outlines initial key issues and recommendations. This initial version will then be shared with stakeholders across various sectors, including industry experts, policymakers, and academic researchers, through multiple rounds of stakeholder discussions (also organised by deCYPher).

These discussions will provide valuable feedback, ensuring that the policy recommendations are grounded in practical, real-world considerations and reflect diverse perspectives. The insights gathered from these stakeholder rounds will be used to refine the final policy brief, ensuring that it addresses the most pressing needs and opportunities for AI and synthetic biology integration in Europe.

The development of the policy brief will also observe and take into account ongoing consultations about European regulatory updates, such as current activities of EuropaBio lobbying for an EU Biotech Act¹.

2 FIRST VERSION OF THE POLICY BRIEF

Removing regulatory bottlenecks to strengthen EU competitiveness in bioindustrial applications

Executive summary

The European Union (EU) faces significant challenges in its regulatory framework for bioproduction, particularly in sectors utilising genetically modified organisms (GMOs) for medicine, food, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, fragrances, and biocontrol. Current processes, particularly under the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), are perceived as slower and more cumbersome compared to regulatory systems in other regions, such as the United States, Brazil or China. These inefficiencies, coupled with discrepancies between EU and global regulatory approaches, risk driving innovation and investment to more favorable jurisdictions. While regulations are necessary, in particular with regard to product safety, this brief identifies key issues and offers recommendations to streamline processes, safeguard proprietary information, foster industry engagement, and enable European biotech-innovation.

Key issues

- **Digital sequence information and development:** The Nagoya Protocol, especially when extended to genetic sequences, may create barriers to the exploitation of microbial resources. Unique challenges arise with microorganisms due to their wide distribution, rapid discovery, and crucial role in research. Ambiguities in assigning rights to strains – particularly with airborne bacteria – add complexity and uncertainty for developers, which is expected to impact future research and exploitation using artificial intelligence.
- **Lengthy approval processes:** EFSA reviews for novel products often take years to complete, particularly for applications involving GMOs. By comparison, regulatory bodies like the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and Brazil's National Health Surveillance Agency (ANVISA) have more streamlined processes. Feedback from European companies in research projects indicates some review processes have taken up to 10 years, which is problematic as this means Europe is losing valuable time compared to other world regions, specifically as patent protection is capped at 20 years. Sectors like fragrance (non-food chemicals) benefit from faster REACH processes under the European Chemicals Agency, but broader harmonisation is lacking.

¹ <https://www.europabio.org/the-eu-biotech-act/>

- **Disparities in requirements:** EU regulations often require full genomic disclosure and extensive genetic stability studies, including for products where neither genetically modified organisms nor their DNA are present in the final product. Disclosing proprietary genetic information exposes companies to potential intellectual property theft, particularly in jurisdictions with less stringent confidentiality protections. Other regions employ risk-tiered approaches, where lower-risk products are fast-tracked, reducing regulatory burdens without compromising safety. For example, ANVISA has established specific pathways to license follow-on biological products (or biosimilars), including a more permissive individual development pathway.
- **Global competition:** Businesses are increasingly relocating bioengineering projects to jurisdictions with faster approval times and lower compliance costs. This shift threatens EU economic growth and its standing in global biotechnology markets. The US dominates the biotechnology market, followed by the EU and then China, however emerging economies like South Korea and Brazil are swiftly catching up.

Policy recommendations

1. **Protect proprietary information:** Evaluate necessity for disclosing genetic information in low-risk products or applications. Develop robust data protection measures and protocols to ensure genomic data and proprietary research disclosed during regulatory reviews are safeguarded.
2. **Accelerate regulatory timelines:** Establish clear deadlines for EFSA evaluations, ensuring they align with international benchmarks. Introduce expedited pathways for low-risk applications or products, especially if the final product does not contain GMOs nor modified DNA. Evaluate the use of AI, in conjunction with human experts, to support fast and high quality assessment of regulatory applications.
3. **Harmonise requirements with international standards:** Adopt a tiered regulatory approach, aligning with practices in the US and Brazil. This would enable the EU to maintain safety standards while improving efficiency.
4. **Foster industry engagement:** Continue to foster collaboration between policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers to identify and address practical barriers to compliance as well as emerging challenges.

Conclusion

The EU must adapt its regulatory processes to remain competitive in the rapidly evolving bioproduction landscape. By streamlining approval processes, harmonising standards, and ensuring robust protections for researchers and companies, Europe can reestablish its leadership in innovation and drive growth in bioengineering industries once regulatory barriers are reduced.

3 TOWARDS THE FINAL POLICY BRIEF

The final policy brief will comprise an executive summary of Deliverable 6.4, our stakeholder mapping exercise (due August 31st, 2026). The stakeholder mapping exercise and analysis of the stakeholder roundtables will provide feedback on deCYPher's approach and results to the project consortium and upon reflection allows for an adaptation of the work plan to accommodate suggestions and grasp opportunities. Additional observations on e.g. societal ramification of AI/ML will also be included in the final version of the policy brief presenting recommendations and aiding non-specialised audiences (e.g. policy makers) to make informed decisions.

The final policy brief (Deliverable 6.6) will be due on May 31st, 2027.